

Studies on Quantity-Intensity Relations of Potassium Availability in some Soils of West Bengal

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Studies on quantity/intensity (Q/I) relations of potassium (K) have been conducted using eight soils of West Bengal with contrasting properties. Several important parameters have been evaluated and their dependence on soil properties discussed. The poolsize of labile K as well as its lability in soils were found to follow the equilibrium activity ratios (AR_o^K). The influence of Gapon exchange selectivity coefficients (K_G) on Q/I relationships of the given soils was also ascertained. The approximate validity of the $(CEC \cdot K_G)$ products leading to the PBC_o^K of the soils was put to a test for the given soils with encouraging results. The use of the interpolated K_G values at $\Delta K_{exch}=0$ in assessing the potassium availability in the given soils was further ascertained.

The quantity/intensity (Q/I) studies¹ involve the change in exchangeable K (quantity) as a function of K activity ratio, $(a_k / \sqrt{a_{Ca+Mg}})$ (Intensity). These studies have been used for better understanding of K^+ release into the soil solution and consequent uptake by plants². From the Q/I plot, several parameters may be obtained to characterise the K-status and K-release characteristics of soil, namely, the equilibrium activity ratio for K (AR_o^K), labile or exchangeable K ($-\Delta K_o$), potential buffering capacity for K at AR_o^K (PBC_o^K), and specifically fixed potassium (K_x)³.

Theoretical :

For the K-(Ca+Mg) interaction, the Gapon equation leads to

$$K_G = \frac{[\text{Exch.K}] (A_{Ca+Mg})^{1/2}}{[\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] (A_K)} \quad (1)$$

where K_G is the Gapon cation-exchange selectivity coefficient $(\text{mol dm}^{-3})^{-1/2}$, Exch, the exchangeable cations $(\text{in cmol (p}^+) \text{ kg}^{-1})$ and A the activity ratio for the cations shown. K_G values may be plotted as a function of changes in exchangeable K-levels on treatment of soil with K/Ca solutions, and its interpolated value at $\Delta K_{exch}=0$ may be taken to provide a measure of the inherent K availability in the soil⁴. Equation (1) can be rearranged as

$$[\text{Exch.K}] = [\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] \cdot K (A_K) / (A_{Ca+Mg})^{1/2}$$

or, $[\text{Exch.K}] = [\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] \cdot K_G \cdot AR_k \quad (2)$

$$\text{or, } \frac{d[\text{Exch.K}]}{d[AR^K]} = [\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] K_G$$

$$\text{or, } PBC^K = [\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] \cdot K_G \quad (3)$$

For most agricultural soils under K-fertilisation, the contribution of Exch.K to the CEC is insignificant⁵, i.e.

$$[\text{Exch.Ca} + \text{Exch.Mg}] \gg [\text{Exch.K}]$$

and equation (3) may be approximated as

$$PBC^K \cong CEC \cdot K_G \quad (4)$$

In the present study, the Q/I parameters for potassium dynamics in several soils of West Bengal are evaluated. Attempts are also made to ascertain the influence of the Gapon selectivity coefficient (K_G) for K-(Ca+Mg) exchange in soils on Q/I relationship as well as the relationship of PBC_o^K and CEC with the Q/I parameters of the given soils.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the important properties of the soils studied. The soil samples from Mondouri, Chinsurah, Mohitnagar and Canning exhibited rather high CEC values. The clay content was quite high in the Chinsurah, Bolpur, Canning and Mondouri soils whereas other soils did not show high clay contents.

Table 2 gives a summary of the distribution of different forms of potassium. The Canning, Chinsurah and Mondouri soils showed large reserves of exchangeable K. The non-exchangeable potassium or reserve potassium being an index of K availability under stress situation, the Mondouri, Canning, Chinsurah and Mohitnagar soils are expected to release K under stress condition more effectively than the other soils studied (Table 2). This seems to be directly correlated to the dominance in the clay fraction of the given soils of micaceous minerals. Thus, substantial amounts of illite were present in the Canning,

TABLE 1—IMPORTANT PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Location of soil	Soil order	Dominant clay minerals present	pH (1 : 2.5) Soil : Water suspension	EC dS m ⁻¹	C.E.C. cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Organic carbon g kg ⁻¹	Clay %	Exchangeable (Ca ²⁺ +Mg ²⁺) cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Exchangeable Na ⁺ cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹
Mondouri	Entisol	Illite	7.78	0.45	28.4	6.30	44.8	26.7	1.47
Chinsurah	Entisol	Smectite	7.36	0.30	36.5	10.7	64.8	31.4	1.04
Burdwan	Inceptisol	Smectite	5.74	0.20	11.3	4.00	22.3	4.80	0.28
Mohitnagar	Mollisol	Illite	6.02	0.17	23.7	19.2	24.8	3.60	0.32
Bolpur	Ultisol	Kaolinite	5.96	0.07	17.7	4.50	54.8	14.2	0.45
Midnapore	Ultisol	Kaolinite	5.50	0.14	10.1	1.70	19.8	3.20	0.35
Anandapur	Ultisol	Kaolinite	5.62	0.18	10.9	4.30	14.8	4.60	0.29
Canning	Entisol	Illite	6.70	4.80	21.2	4.60	59.8	19.4	1.42

TABLE 2—DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF POTASSIUM IN SOILS

Location of soil	Water soluble potassium	Exchangeable potassium cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Non-exchangeable potassium
Mondouri	0.04	0.40	5.75
Chinsurah	0.15	0.58	4.13
Burdwan	0.12	0.28	1.67
Mohitnagar	0.03	0.14	3.34
Bolpur	0.03	0.21	2.25
Midnapore	0.07	0.11	0.32
Anandapur	0.19	0.23	0.38
Canning	0.16	0.41	6.76

Mohitnagar and Mondouri soils⁶. The Chinsurah and Bolpur soils, despite being dominant, respectively, in smectite and kaolinite, contained considerable amounts of illitic clays, the former soil having it more⁷. The Midnapore and Anandapur soils, on the other hand, were dominant in kaolinite⁶. The clay fraction in the Burdwan soil was rich in smectite and contained relatively less amount of illite⁶.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the Q/I plots of two representative soils, namely, the Bolpur and Chinsurah soils. The form of these Q/I curves was characterised by an upper linear part (non-specific sites for K adsorption and similar to that encountered for Gapon's exchange relationship), and curvilinear part at low equilibrium activity ratio (AR_0^K) values, attributed to exchange with high specific affinity for K⁺. Table 3 records various Q/I parameters.

Le Roux⁸ noted that ΔK^0 was a better estimate of soil labile K than the normal exchangeable K⁺. He found that the higher values of labile K ($-\Delta K^0$) indicated a greater K⁺ release into the soil solution resulting in a larger pool of labile K. Indeed for the present soils, the labile K was always higher for each soil. This may possibly be attributed to the presence of specific sites (K_x) in the given soils

Table 3 gives the Q/I parameters of the soils used. The Chinsurah soil having the highest value of PBC_0^K will be able to maintain the activity ratio in spite of the change in ΔK . The Midnapore, Mohitnagar, Burdwan and Anandapur soils have

Fig. 1. Q/I curve for Bolpur soil.

rather small buffering capacity. These soils are thus expected to be susceptible to rapid changes in the AR^K with change in ΔK , and would require more frequent K fertilisation (than the Chinsurah soil) on long-term intensive cultivation.

The Q/I curves being largely convex in shape for the present soils, the corresponding buffering capacities tended to be inversely proportional to the activity ratio⁹.

The PBC_0^K of a soil is a measure of the amount of labile K a soil can supply at a given energy

 Fig. 2. Q/I curve for Chinsurah soil.

TABLE 3—QUANTITY/INTENSITY PARAMETERS OF POTASSIUM IN SOILS

Location of soil	$10^3 AR_e^K$ (mol dm ⁻³) ^{1/2}	Labile K ⁺ (-ΔK ⁰) cmol(p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	PBC ₀ ^K cmol (p ⁺)kg ⁻¹ (mol dm ⁻³) ^{1/2}	Specifically fixed pota- ssium (K _x) cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Interpo- lated K _G (from K _G vs K _{exch} mol plots) mol dm ⁻³) ^{1/2}
Mondouri	5.20	0.42	80.0	0.16	3.3
Chinsurah	4.25	0.60	150.0	0.28	6.3
Burdwan	26.0	0.43	16.6	0.12	3.4
Mohitnagar	9.50	0.16	18.1	0.13	5.6
Bolpur	7.50	0.27	40.0	0.11	4.5
Midnapore	16.0	0.17	9.20	0.08	5.6
Anandapur	11.5	0.25	20.0	0.05	4.6
Canning	12.0	0.48	40.0	0.12	4.4

level. It, therefore, indicates the ability of a soil to maintain the intensity of K⁺ in the soil solution and is proportional to CEC¹⁰. This is in agreement with the present results shown by a positive correlation between CEC and PBC₀^K ($r=0.892^{**}$).

An approximate validity of the (CEC.K_G) product in evaluating the PBC₀^K, provided that the exchangeable K is low compared to the CEC of the soil (vide equation 4), is evident from a highly significant linear relationship between the product, (K_G.CEC) and PBC₀^K ($r=0.843^{**}$). Here, the K_G values used were the interpolated values recorded in Table 3. Generally, it may be assumed that a number of different soils, in which K release in soil solution is controlled by K-(Ca+Mg) interactions, could have the same PBC₀^K provided (i) they also have equal CEC and K_G values (i.e. equation 4), or else (ii) high or low CEC values for such soils are offset by equally low or high K_G values, respectively⁵.

Acquaye and Maclean¹¹ reported that a higher PBC₀^K tended to be associated with higher amounts of clay which represented a major source of K released from exchange sites. This trend finds a support from the results obtained for the given soils as demonstrated by the corresponding simple linear correlation coefficient ($r=0.754^*$). It was also reasonably satisfactory to note a positive relationship between K_G (interpolated values), taken from Table 3, and the exchangeable K values for the present soils indicating the use of such interpolated K_G value as an index of K availability in the given soils.

Experimental

Eight surface soil samples (0–15 cm) were collected from different sites in West Bengal, namely, Mondouri (Entisol), Chinsurah (Entisol), Burdwan (Inceptisol), Mohitnagar (Mollisol), Bolpur (Ultisol), Midnapore (Ultisol), Anandapur (Ultisol) and Canning (Entisol). The soils were air-dried and passed through a 2-mm sieve. Important soil properties are presented in Table 1. The various forms of K present in these soil samples were obtained by using different extractants. The water-soluble, exchangeable and non-exchangeable potassium were determined by following the methods adopted from Jackson¹², Grewal and Kanwar¹³ and Pratt¹⁴. The data are presented in Table 2.

For studying the Q/I relationship and PBC₀^K of the given soils, the methodology recommended by Hesse¹⁵ was adopted.

The gain or loss of potassium by the soil (i.e. ΔK or Q in cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹) was obtained as the differences in concentration of the initial and the final solutions after equilibration with the soil. The intensity (I) or activity ratio (AR^K) was calculated by determining the activities of K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions from the knowledge of molar concentrations of K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions in the soil extracts, and the activity coefficients of these ions were obtained from the ionic strength of the equilibrium solution using Davies equation¹⁶. For the purpose, the ionic strength (I) was calculated from the electrical conductivity (EC_e) of the soil

extracts according to a relation proposed by Griffin and Jurinak¹⁷ namely,

$$I=0.0127 EC_0$$

The Q/I plots were obtained by showing quantity (ΔK) against AR^K . From the Q/I curve, the potential buffering capacity was determined from the gradient of the curve by extrapolation of the linear portion of the curve to cut the Q axis¹. A number of Q/I curves, however, do not have an extensive linear form, and the question arises as to which point of the curve should be used to calculate the PBC^K . Quemener¹⁸ described the buffering capacity in terms of the slope of the curve at $\Delta K=0$. The PBC^K values, so obtained, may be denoted as PBC_0^K , and taken as a measure of $d(\Delta K)/d(AR^K)$ at AR_0^K .

The Gapon exchange selectivity coefficient (K_G) was calculated from the K, Ca and Mg activities determined in the Q/I procedure discussed above, plus the exchangeable K, Ca and Mg levels in the soils at equilibrium determined by extraction with neutral NH_4OAc . The K_G values for different sets were finally plotted as function of the corresponding changes in the exchangeable K. The K_G values interpolated from the plot at $\Delta K_{exch}=0$, were taken to provide measures of K availability in the given soils. These interpolated K_G values are shown in Table 3.

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